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The primary characteristics of English pragmatics in Applied Linguistics

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Abstract

Pragmatics is an important linguistic subject that defines the hidden meanings of a writer and speaker with regard to the linguistic effort. It is indicated together with its user. In practical terms, the attention is frequently placed on a contextual meaning in which every other meaning of the context is spoken by both the writer and the speaker who desires to convey anything. The field of pragmatics therefore helps to deal with the intended meaning of the speaker. It is the scope of pragmatics that shows some language terms. They are often expressed as instructive contributions through the physical or real expression of meaning, the use of words, the structure and the arrangement of the discussions. The second is a speech act focusing on what someone is told by the writer and the speaker. Thus, the main objective of pragmatics is to communicate using the addressor's intended words.

Keywords: Speech Act, Maxims, Politeness, Deixis, Positive face, Negative face.

1. INTRODUCTION

Communication is one of the simplest tasks of a language since it establishes when people wish to convey their intended meanings. Without a language, it is nearly hard to speak with others and be a vital part of a discourse aimed at communicating about a specific circumstance. Pragmatics is inextricably tied to the area of semantics, as both are concerned with the formation and elaboration of meaning. Semantics is the study of the literary meaning directed towards the speaker or writer that is connected to the individual and the external world (Yule, 1996). Semantics establish connections between the verbal and the descriptive that generate it in the form of speech and writing (Yule, 1996).

Whereas the discipline of Pragmatics is concerned with the study of form and its user, who arranges the provided forms in various ways in order to engage in discourse. In pragmatics, individuals engage in

self-reflection in order to comprehend the implied meaning, as well as their own distinct aims, purposes, and the speaker's actions. In this study, one of the key implications of pragmatics is toward a speaker who wishes to impart contextual meaning to the listener based on the presented scenario.

Thus, Pragmatics is primarily concerned with meaning and its definition of role variation in relation to various communicative duties offered by the speaker in a way that a reader or listener can interpret. The following study concerns the broad understanding of persons in terms of what they typically mean in a specific setting and their influence within that context. All of this is possible through the course of communication between the utterer and the speaker. As a result, pragmatics is defined as the study of contextual meaning.

2. AUTHOR'S DEFINITION

Pragmatics is not just concerned with the meaning-making of a given sentence; it is also concerned with the speaker's concealed meaning. One could argue that pragmatics is the study of what is unsaid. It is dependent on the speaker's concept of what s/he want to communicate to the listener in various settings. It is through pragmatics that a listener or reader can examine the intended meanings, allowing them to research their purposes, within their assumptions, and to explore them in the shape of behavior in state to various acts they wish to execute when speaking with a front audience.

According to Crystal (1987:62-5), pragmatics is concerned with the elements that influence the language we use and its consequences on others. Thus, the pragmatic variables that influence our choice of grammatical structure are the sound pattern and the meaning that we are making by presenting the vocabulary in the intended manner as a means of communication (Crystal, 1987:62-5). Thus, pragmatics tends to be associated with the meaning of words used by people in their social contexts and their choice of words in a context.

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According to Robin, the area of pragmatics is defined as the study of phenomena revolving around the various aspects affecting speech situations (1964:23).

Leech (1983:13-4), stated that pragmatics is the study of meaning and the way that speech is related to any provided situations, as well as an aspect of how a speech is made in a situation, and it also paves the way for determining a core principle regarding whether it deals with semantic or pragmatic phenomena. The main significant components of pragmatics imply that it is the study of meaning in relation to speech situations. Within pragmatics, the following five critical features have been highlighted:

a) Addressees or addressers (hearer and speaker) b) An utterance in context, Leech agreed on the importance of appropriate utterances in social and physical settings, but he placed a greater emphasis on contextual information.

c) Leech describes both the objectives of an utterance and the meaning of the intention to say it.

d) The utterance is a type of action or act; in pragmatics, verbal utterances can also be performed in the manner of acts to meet the needs of a given scenario.

e) The utterance that is in the form of enclosed verbal acts does have a tendency to identify for sentence or token tagging that are not, in fact, sentences, but can be the piece of language that classifies as short and long single sentence.

3. PRAGMATICS APPLICATION LINGUISTICS

Pragmatics is concerned with meaning and is concerned with the fundamental way in which meaning and its relationship to reality are viewed. As it is for comparable theories of meaning, which regard language as systematic in its ability to designate numerous concrete entities and their symbols. The truth about semantics, which focuses on the meaning and purpose of the phrase, is that it analyzes many meaning forms in a formal manner and also deals with surface meaning. However, it is devoid of a contextual definition. In layman's terms, semantics is concerned with the general structure of sentences and with determining the lexical condition of the content that formulates meaning information from other sources (Chapman 2000). A language can also deal with a variety of other instruments, including the instrument of thought and the instrument of social action (Capone, 2005).

Thus, within the realm of pragmatics, the following major words can be defined:

The Utterance is defined as the physical and clear unit of meaning that conveys information in the contribution through the following: a) The words used, b) The sentence structure, c) The setting of the conversation within the context in which it is used, d) The senses of the start in a particular context, and e) The use of gesture to convey the meaning.

One of the most significant items gathered from these sources is the context utterance, which is provided with background knowledge in order to communicate an informational message to the other sections of the dialogue, similar to any written text.

4. SPEECH ACT

The use and perspective of social interactionists on any language can be summarized as linguistic phenomena that are expressed through speech acts. When the speaker has something to say to someone, speech acts that deal with social activity. In the case of a writer, who creates something for another person in order to impart meaning to the listener, with-in a given location and time. Speech acts can even reinforce this assumption by indicating that they engage the speaker with the hearer in the form of communication, indicating that the speaker wishes to impart information to the hearer. A speech act is a spoken statement that is primarily concerned with addressing a specific issue in the communication. The concept of speech acts was proposed for the first time by the British philosopher John Langshaw Austin (1911-1960), who worked at Oxford and clarified his concept through a series of delivered lectures that were even published prior to his death in 1962. The title of the book is "How to do things with words." Austin expresses philosophy's language in terms of preserving one of the primary tasks of language, which is to carry out substantial social acts. The concern of the speech acts determines how language is used.

Speech acts are specific verbs that are employed within sentences to help classify them. Austin describes his concept appropriately in order to illustrate the distinctions between two important verbs, "performative and constative."

The formal usage of verbs as 'Constative' and describing them in the form of reality, for example, 'Rain' in the sentence 'Through the week, it poured severely'. Certain statements have a truth value yet are judged as true or untrue. On the other hand, 'Performative verbs' are used differently; they operate as instruments to accomplish the

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aims of interaction between two or more speakers. The most applicable example is the verb 'promise,' which deals exclusively with linguistic acts. The use of promise within a sentence, for example, "I promise I will assist you with your assignment or work," expresses the speaker's honest desire to do so in the future.

4.1. DIFFERENT TYPES OF SPEECH ACTS

When someone delivers a speech, they perform three distinct acts. All of these utterances can be classed further as speech acts:

1) Locutionary Acts: This form of speech act is frequently directed at the speaker when he expresses a particular reference and sense. The grammatical principle also applies to the speaker in this particular dialogue. A locutionary act is typically performed by the speaker as sequences of messages are connected to produce the phrase, which is typically one that deals with the value of truth.

For instance, the Earth is circular.

Birds soar through the sky.

2) An Illocutionary Act: In this case, the speaker utilizes a per-formative verb to communicate the sentence's intents.

For instance, I christen his ship.

3) Elocutionary Acts: This sort of act is concerned with the linguistic effect of an action.

However, when the speaker imparts meaning to the hearer, the perlocutionary activities have a very obvious effect on the speaker. Examples include offending, convicting, startling, and influencing someone.

4.2 IMPLICATIONS OF CONVERSATION IN THE FIELD OF PRAGMATICS

Grice (1988-93), a renowned English philosopher, has placed a greater emphasis on the work of regular human behavior as documented in their discourse.

His intention was to introduce the concept of 'conversational implicatures,' in which the speaker's implications had been pre-determined during their discussions. According to Grice, a discussion must have certain maxims in order to decrease the intended meaning. Grice recognizes four major maxims throughout their discourse.

4.3 THE FOLLOWING ARE FOUR CONVERSATIONAL MAXIMS

a) Quality: Quality is defined as "what speakers say must be presumed to be true."

b) Quantity: Quantity refers to the extent to which speakers must be informative, but not excessively so.

c) Relevance: The speaker must be pertinent to the exchange's aim.

d) Attitude: The speaker's tone must be clear and without ambiguity.

Additionally, Grice has emphasized the speaker's cooperation principle. These tacit agreements during conversations are these maxims. These agreements are made because of these maxims, which make it easy to interpret what the speaker is trying to convey in various contexts.

Grice's maxims are those that can be consciously affected while speaking in a sarcastic or sardonic tone. It is, indeed, a method of deception. Grice has made reference to relevance theory throughout his creation of conversational implicatures. Deirdre Wilson and Dan Sperber, two linguists, have been more concerned with the concept of relevance to the structure of a dialogue, which maintains the contribution of relevant processes toward matching a context to the addressee's assumptions.

5. POLITENESS

Politeness is a broad term that refers to a speaker's attitude toward the addressee's differing wishes in various situations. In year, English linguists Levinson and Penelope Brown will examine the linguistic expressions of politeness (1979). They offered several significant tactics for bridging the disparities in maximizing in interactions, such as the use of formal language in terms of address or indirect speech acts. The purpose of these strategies is to provide a means of accomplishing specific objectives. As a result, there is a predetermined order in which to address an addressee. One of the primary names used to describe these methods is "face," which refers to the face that reflects the speaker's self-image in public and can be classified into two broad categories.

- Positive facial expression.
- Negative facial expression

5.1 POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE FACE

Positive facial expressions convey the individual's wishes and can be acknowledged and respected by others.

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A negative face expresses the desire to speak about social behavior without being constrained by a limited set of options. As a result, Politeness serves as the face of the other. The act of face saving is associated with a social action that signifies one's uniqueness. It demonstrates the significance of inner desire and fear. On the other hand, a face-threatening conduct might have an effect on the actions of others; it may be interpreted as an insult. There are numerous linguistic ways for diminishing a threat's negative face. For instance, to annoy someone or to apologize in a positive manner for highlighting a point about a shared interest in something, or to make a proposal to an addressee.

5.2 DEIXIS

Language is a means of referring to and highlighting major issues in daily life. The term deixis is taken from the Greek and meaning 'display' and 'reference'. Additionally, deixis can be interpreted as (deiksqs/or daiksqs). Numerous assumptions are possible for this word. A key term in discourse has been introduced. It was a case of pronominal reference, in which a pronoun made reference to a noun in order to perform its function. This form can also play a critical function in the field of pragmatics and the other two branches of Deixis, as demonstrated by its critical role in language. One of them is the temporal domain of language; it illustrates how language uses terms to represent time or points for expressing time. For instance, later, tomorrow, now, prior to, and today. There are tenses in language. There are three tenses, just as there are in the English language. That is, the present, the past, and the future. Additionally, the future perfect tense can perform essential activities over time. Deixis's second domain is dubbed spatial. The spatial works to explain a collection of options derived from adverbs and prepositions such as down, over, above, under, beneath, and across. The English language has two primary methods for indicating and showing pronouns. They are as follows:

- One is the object that is adjacent to the speaker
- Two is the thing that is distant from the speaker.

It is referred to as that/this in the English language.

6. CONCLUSION

In summary, it is reasonable to believe that the preceding brief examinations of English pragmatics have not limited their scope to specific goals; rather, they can be connected to other aspects of human practical desires to communicate their views. The work is focused on

developing a model for speaking and writing in order to meet required criteria for communicating a message within a prioritized situation base. The definitions and scope of pragmatics within the primary scientific subject of linguistics stated above can be ended with the fact that studying pragmatics assists future researchers in governing their studies concerning elements affecting speaker choice. Additionally, these will impart knowledge of language in a given social interaction that influences the choice of personal race expressed in ideas contained inside words spoken to others. According to David Crystal, pragmatics enables us to delve deeper into offered meanings by moving beyond an apparent set of words free of ambiguity. It's also understandable, as David Crystal puts it, that "Baby Sale has a lot of bargains." The concept of contextual information is precisely communicated with the speaker or writer of the text in pragmatics. Whereas the meaning conveyed by context is not precise enough to define the semantic properties of the words expressed. Thus, the David Crystal model can be used as a theoretical framework for studying pragmatics in applied linguistics. However, pragmatics is distinct from semantics in that it is concerned with meaning beyond the words, whereas semantics is concerned with the interpretation of words as figurative meanings.

REFERENCES:

Capone (2005). Pragmemes (a comparative study of English and Italian). 37, 1355-1371 Journal of Pragmatics

D. M. Boudreau & R. S. Chapman (2000). The relationship between event representation and language ability in children's and teenagers' narratives with Down syndrome. 43(5), 1146-1159. Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research.

David Crystal (1985). A Linguistics and Phonetics Dictionary. Second ed. Blackwell, Oxford, 240. Print

H. P. Grice (1989). Studies in the use of language. Published by Harvard University Press.

R. T. Lakoff (1964). Stylistic strategies in style grammar. Language, Sex, and Gender: New York Academy of Sciences Vol.327, pp. 53-78, edited by J. Orasanu et al.

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S. Levinson and B. Penelope (1987). Politeness. Several uni-versal patterns of language usage. University Press, Cambridge.

G. Yule (1996). Pragmatics. University Press, Oxford